

Relative Efficacies of Cationic and Anionic Surfactants and Their Mixtures in the Suppression of Polarographic Negative Maximum of Co(II)

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The suppression of polarographic negative maximum of Co(II) has been attempted by various cationic and anionic surfactants viz., cetyl pyridium bromide (CPB), cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB), cetyl dimethyl benzyl ammonium chloride (CDBAC), sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), dodecyl benzene sulphonate (DBS), dioctyl sodium sulphosuccinate (DSSS), dibutyl sodium sulphosuccinate (DBSS) and tergitol-7. The relative efficacies of these surfactants and their mixtures have been established on the basis of the kinetic parameter αn_a , calculated by Koutecky's method. A comparison of ' αn_a ' values at the stage where maximum just disappears gives the relative efficacies of cationic and anionic surfactants and also an insight into their additive or antagonistic influence in the mixture.

RAM *et al*¹ have reported the suppression of polarographic maximum due to Co(II) system by various ionic and non-ionic surfactants and have compared their relative efficacies on the basis of characteristic properties, viz., maximum suppression point² (M.S.P.), specific suppression coefficient³ (S.S.C.) and critical micelle concentration² (C.M.C.). Recently, Singh and coworkers⁴ have determined the efficacies of various metal ions in the suppression of the negative maximum of Ni(II) in terms of kinetic parameter ' αn_a '. However, this quantitative aspect of the study based on the influence of various ionic and non-ionic surfactants on the kinetics of the irreversible electrode reaction of Co(II) vis-a-vis the suppression of its maximum has not been attempted so far. Moreover, according to Kuta^{1,6} very interesting results can be obtained if two surfactants of opposite signs are used as suppressor in their mixture as this would give rise to the additive or antagonistic effects of cationic and anionic surfactants in the suppression of the negative maximum of Co(II). This has not been investigated so far. The present paper deals with the determination of the efficacies of some cationic and anionic surfactants in the suppression of the negative maximum of Co(II), on the basis of the parameter ' αn_a '. Besides this, an attempt has been made to study the additive or antagonistic effects of cationic and anionic surfactants and their mixtures with regard to the suppression of the negative maximum of Co(II).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R., BDH grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity

water. The depolarizer concentration was kept at $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. $NaNO_3$ (0.1 M) was used as the supporting electrolyte. A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CL02) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL 50) was used for measuring the potential and current respectively. Deoxygenation of the solutions was done by passing through the solution a steady stream of purified nitrogen gas. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.) was used as a reference electrode. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics: $m = 1.673$ mg/sec, $t = 4.04$ sec, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 1.778$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/2}, $h_{corr} = 63.0$ cm.

Results and Discussion

After the suppression of maximum by the requisite amounts of the surfactants, Co(II) yields, in each case, a well-defined diffusion-controlled wave. On applying various criteria of irreversibility⁵⁻⁸, it has been ascertained that the electrode reaction of Co(II) is totally irreversible in presence of different amounts of cationic and anionic surfactants as well as their mixtures. The value of the kinetic parameter αn_a has been calculated by Koutecky's method⁹.

From Table I it is evident that αn_a tends to decrease with the increase in the concentration of each surfactant. αn_a values (and subsequent estimation of α) give a measure of the extent to which kinetics of the electrode reaction is influenced. An attempt to estimate n_a (the number of electrons, involved in the rate determining step) leads to a conclusion that n_a is equal to 2. However, according to Meites¹⁰ only a single electron can be transferred

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at a time and a value of n_a exceeding 1 would not necessarily mean that two electrons are actually added simultaneously but merely indicates that the successive steps occur simultaneously and cannot be distinguished on the time scale implicit in the polarographic measurement. Since the decrease in αn_a values is indiscrete and at no stage the two consecutive values vary by a factor of 2, the possibility of decrease in the value of the product αn_a due to the change in n_a is ruled out. Thus it can be concluded that the value of α is decreasing¹¹. α , the transfer coefficient, signifies¹² the fraction of the applied voltage which favours the cathodic reaction, $\text{Co}^{2+} + 2e \rightarrow \text{Co}$. A decrease in the value of α thus implies that the transfer of electron/electrons is made increasingly difficult. In other words, the electrode reaction is rendered increasingly more irreversible. A decrease in i_d and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ with an increase in the concentration of both the cationic and anionic surfactants lend support to this conclusion.

Relative efficacies of surfactants in terms of αn_a values :

At the stage where the polarographic maximum due to Co(II) system just disappears, the order of αn_a value signifies the extent to which the addition of cationic and anionic surfactants renders the electrode reaction more irreversible compared to that in the absence of these surfactants. In other words, a surfactant for which αn_a has got higher value at the point of just suppression will be more effective with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electrode reaction. In the present study the order of αn_a values for different surfactants is as follows :

Cationic : CTAB > CDBAC

Anionic : Tergitol-7 > DBS > DBSS > SLS > DSSS

Thus among the cationic surfactants CTAB eliminates the maximum of Co(II) with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electron transfer than CDBAC. On the other hand among the anionic surfactants Tergitol-7 eliminates the maximum with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electron transfer followed by DBS, DBSS, SLS and DSSS.

A comparison of αn_a values at the point of just suppression in respect of the mixtures of cationic and anionic surfactants shows that in the mixtures of CTAB and SLS, CTAB and DSSS and CDBAC and DSSS, the value of αn_a is larger in comparison to its value when these surfactants are added separately. From this it follows that the influence of CTAB and SLS and those of DSSS with CTAB and CDBAC is additive as they eliminate the maximum of Co(II) with less influence on the kinetics of the electrode process. On the other hand in mixtures of CTAB and DBS CTAB

and Tergitol-7, CDBAC and DBS, and CDBAC and DBSS, the value of αn_a is larger in comparison to cationic surfactants (CTAB and CDBAC) while it is lesser than the anionic ones (DBS, DBSS and Tergitol-7). From this it follows that the influence of CTAB and DBS, CTAB and Tergitol-7, CDBAC and DBS and CDBAC and DBSS in their mixtures is antagonistic.

A comparison of αn_a values for cationic and anionic surfactants reveals that these are higher for anionic surfactants than the cationic ones. From this it follows that anionic surfactants suppress the negative maximum of Co(II) with lesser influence on the kinetics of the electron transfer.

The effects of surfactants on electron-transfer processes- that is, on the reversibility of an electrode reaction and on the parameters αn_a and $k'_{t,h}$ for irreversible electrode reactions—result¹³ from the changes in the structure of the double layer. The adsorbed molecules displace ions from the Helmholtz layer, thereby altering the charge distribution. They may also displace the reaction surface away from the electrode. Both the effects alter the potential at the reaction surface. In addition, a bridge that may serve to effect electron transfer from the electrode to an ion or molecule at the reaction surface when the surfactant is absent may become difficult to envisage when it is present ; the entire mechanism of the electron-transfer process may change.

A decrease in i_d and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ (vide Tables 1 and 2) with increasing concentrations of surfactants indicate¹⁴ the inhibition of the electrode process of Co(II). This is due¹⁵ to the increase in surface-coverage of the electrode (d.m.e.).

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS DUE TO Co(II) SYSTEM IN PRESENCE OF SURFACTANTS

Surfactant	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V (S.C.E.)	$D \times 10^6$ cm^2/sec	αn_a
<i>Cationic</i>				
CPB ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)	wave drawn out			
CTAB ($5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)	14.44	1.27	8.27	0.49
($1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$)	13.68	1.29	7.42	0.46
CDBAC ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)	13.30	1.32	7.01	0.48
($2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$)	11.40	1.33	5.15	0.46
<i>Anionic</i>				
SLS ($7.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)	12.92	1.33	6.62	0.74
($1.5 \times 10^{-3} M$)	12.16	1.36	5.86	0.69
DBS ($2.4 \times 10^{-3} M$)	11.93	1.28	5.56	0.92
($1.4 \times 10^{-3} M$)	10.77	1.29	4.60	0.82
Tergitol-7 ($4.4 \times 10^{-3} M$)	13.68	1.31	7.42	0.98
($8.4 \times 10^{-3} M$)	12.16	1.32	5.86	0.92
DSSS ($4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)	15.58	1.37	9.63	0.53
($1.2 \times 10^{-3} M$)	14.44	1.40	8.27	0.51
DBSS ($8.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)	15.50	1.34	9.53	0.77
($1.4 \times 10^{-3} M$)	13.68	1.37	7.42	0.74

* Indicates the concentration of surfactant at which the maximum just disappears.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS DUE TO Co(II) SYSTEM IN PRESENCE OF SURFACTANT MIXTURES

Surfactant Mixture	i_d #A	$-E_{1/2}$ V (S.C.E.)	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² /sec	αn_a
CTAB ($2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) + SLS ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$)	15.20	1.37	9.16	0.96
" ($1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) + " ($5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$)	13.68	1.40	7.42	0.87
CTAB ($2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) + DBS ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$)	14.82	1.39	8.71	0.77
" ($1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) + " ($5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$)	10.26	1.40	4.17	0.74
CTAB ($1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) + Tergitol-7 ($6.0 \times 10^{-5} M$)	10.26	1.29	4.17	0.74
" ($5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) + " ($1.4 \times 10^{-5} M$)	8.74	1.29	3.03	0.72
CTAB ($3.4 \times 10^{-5} M$) + DBSS ($3.4 \times 10^{-5} M$)	15.58	1.41	9.63	0.82
" ($7.4 \times 10^{-5} M$) + " ($5.4 \times 10^{-5} M$)	12.92	1.42	6.62	0.77
CDBAC ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) + DBS ($1.2 \times 10^{-5} M$)	13.68	1.37	7.42	0.74
" ($1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) + " ($6.0 \times 10^{-5} M$)	12.16	1.41	5.86	0.60
CDBAC ($2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) + DBSS ($7.0 \times 10^{-4} M$)	12.92	1.36	6.60	0.98
" ($1.2 \times 10^{-4} M$) + " ($2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$)	12.54	1.38	6.28	0.92
CDBAC ($1.2 \times 10^{-5} M$) + DBSS ($4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$)	15.58	1.31	9.63	0.57
" ($3.2 \times 10^{-5} M$) + " ($1.2 \times 10^{-1} M$)	13.68	1.34	7.39	0.56

* Indicates the concentration of surfactants at which the maximum just disappears.

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